

Towards inclusive Open Science

Bridging WO, HBO, and MBO for Regional Impact

GET TO KNOW

What is your (main) affiliation?

- A. University / Academic
- B. HBO / applied university
- C. MBO / Vocational education
- D. Funding body or policy organization
- E. Other

What is your role?

- A. Practitioner
- B. Policy maker or advisor
- C. Researcher
- D. Educator
- E. Other

Our vision

Five cats gathered around schematic plans for a sustainable village in nature | Image created by ChatGPT

Two cats shaking paws in front of sustainable energy production plants and industrial building | Image created by ChatGPT

World Café

- Choose a table
- Assign a table host
- Use sticky notes to write down your ideas
- Discuss and highlight key insights

Round 1: Exploring exclusion

What types of knowledge, voices, or partnerships are **lost** when hbo and mbo are **excluded** from Open Science?

10:00

mins: secs: type:

Switcheroo!

- Table chair remains seated
- Everyone else find a different table
- Same task, new question
- Table chair summarizes key insights from round 1 (1-2 mins)

Round 2: Building inclusion

What practical steps can we take to build Open Science infrastructures that recognize applied, community-driven research?

10:00

mins: secs: type:

Wrap up

- What are your table's main findings for round 1?
- What solutions did you come up with in round 2?
- We will assemble all findings and publish a brief report on zenodo: zenodo.org/records/17352682

What will you take from this conversation into your own work?

All images in this presentation were AI generated. Those on slides 2,3,4 and 13 are from Bres (2025):
Bres, E. E. (2025). A collection of AI generated images visualising various RDM aspects (2.0.0).
Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16925229>